

Additional file 6: Figure S6. Assessment of assay reproducibility in the duplex assay using cortical human samples. Tissue samples of the frontal cortex ($n=16$) were lysed using buffer containing 1% Triton and repeatedly analyzed ($n=5$) using the duplex assay for total and pS129 h-asyn concentration on separate days. Percent variation from the mean value for each sample is plotted for total h-asyn measurements (**A**), for pS129 h-asyn (**B**) and for total to pS129 h-asyn ratio (**C**). Dashed lines indicate $\pm 25\%$ variation while thin lines indicate $\pm 10\%$ variation from mean (0%).